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The Academic Institutionalisation of VET as a Science in the German-speaking Area – A Collective Biographical and Network Analytical Study of Discipline Formation in the 20th Century

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Abstract

The contribution focuses on the internal process of the academic formation and establishment of vocational and business education (VET) as a science or as partial disciplines of educational science in the 20th century. Starting with theories of science (e.g. Stichweh, 2013; Clark 1972) in consideration of the establishment thesis of Reinisch (2009; 2010) and the generation thesis of Zabeck (2006) the study would like to contribute to a deeper understanding of the formation and establishment of VET as a science in the German-speaking area. For this purpose the VET professors of the German-speaking area in the 20th Century, as well as their generational relations (in this contribution initially employment and qualification relations) are considered. The methodological access is achieved through a collective biographical quantitative approach based on a separate SQL database by means of network analysis and visualisations via Gephi.

Keywords

history of VET; establishment of VET (as a science); collective biographical; network analysis

1. Introduction

Reinisch (2009) states in a socio-scientific analysis of vocational and business education (resp. 'Berufs- und Wirtschaftspädagogik' or VET as a science in the German-speaking area) that this has decades ago reached the status of an 'established science' (Clark, 1972; 1974) and is presently hold a status as 'normal science' (Kuhn, 1962; 2014). In this respect, he concludes, it is also part of normal science that the members of the corresponding discipline repeatedly ascertain their own foundations. In this respect, Reinisch sees a considerable need for research (Reinisch, 2009; 2010).

The differentiation process (Stichweh, 2013) of vocational and business education or VET as educational science (partial) disciplines¹ is traditionally described in the corresponding contributions of historical business and vocational education research against the background of the establishment of teacher training programmes for commercial and vocational schools (e.g. Pleiß, 1973; Czycholl, 1974; Zabeck, 2009a; Reinisch, 2010). Accordingly, their non-simultaneous constitution and development (e.g. Zabeck, 2009a; Büchter, Klusmeyer, & Kipp, 2009; Lisop, 2009) is presented primarily as being exogenously induced. Endogenous or inner-scientific differentiation processes (Stichweh, 2013), which focus on the formation of internal scientific systems and are equally important for comprehensive reconstruction, were largely ignored - apart from a few noteworthy approaches (Kipp, & Miller-Kipp, 1994; Klusmeyer, 2001; Reinisch, 2009; 2010). As a result, the relationship between internal and external differentiation of business and vocational education and neighbouring academic (partial and/or sub-) disciplines - such as social pedagogy (e.g. Ostendorf, 2009), nursing pedagogy (e.g. Reiber, & Remme, 2009) or economic education - has so far hardly become the subject of systematic considerations.

Our initial focus is on vocational and business education or VET and its internal differentiation as a communication community of scientists. In a long-term perspective, we are aiming at questions about the development and the internal and external constitution of vocational and business education as well as its relations and demarcation lines to neighbouring (partial and/or sub-) disciplines by the quantitative and qualitative analysis of scientific communication relations. In this respect, our (future) studies should lead to a deeper understanding of the development and shaping of vocational and business education or VET as (partial) discipline(s) and its relevance within educational science.

However, before such wide-ranging analyses or even partial analyses of communicative system formation processes of vocational and business education (and neighbouring partial and/or sub-) disciplines seem possible, a suitable basis, more specifically a population of the units or potentially relevant subjects involved in the communication is required. We want to outline this in a first attempt in the form of a collective-biographical and network-analytical approach. In this contribution, therefore we examine the process of the (academic) development and establishment of the VET as a science or educational science (partial) discipline in the 20th century on the basis of a (partial) theory of scientific research. In this respect, we follow on from the above-mentioned establishment thesis of Reinisch (2009) and sketch the emergence and establishment of the VET against the background of Zabeck's (2006) generational classification along the stage model of the institutionalisation process of scientific disciplines of Clark (1972; 1974) (cf. chapter 2). The central question is whether the VET - as Reinisch states - is an established educational science partial discipline or science in the sense of Clark and whether an establishment period can be narrowed down. The methodological research access (cf. chapter 3) is carried out by a collective-biographical-quantitative data collection (Schröder, 2011) of the employment and qualification relations of the professors² of the business and vocational education. Gephi is used to carry out the network analysis of

¹ If we use the term partial discipline in the following, we assume that this is an established scientific discipline in the sense of Clark (1972, 1974) (cf. chapter 2). The term subdiscipline, on the other hand, is used when this stage does not yet appear to have been reached.

² The data corpus does not currently contain junior professors (W1) and senior lecturers. As a first step, we have placed them on an equal footing with habilitants. In the future, however, the data corpus is to be extended to all habilitated scientists (of vocational and business education) with teaching authority (*venia legendi*) and with independence in research and teaching (without habilitation) and thus includes private and senior lecturers as well as junior professors.

the relevant data of the collective-biographical data corpus. The paper concludes with a short presentation of our first preliminary³ results with the focus on business education⁴ as a part of VET (cf. chapter 4).

2. Theory

In the centre of this contribution we focus on the stages of scientific institutionalisation from Clark (1972; 1974). According to this model, every new discipline's development process begins with the stages of the 'solitary scientist' and of 'amateur science'. This development - which we do not consider here - already took place for the business education in the 19th or at the transition into the 20th century and for vocational education in the 20th century. For an empirical analysis of this period, plenty of data on the actors involved and the emerging institutions are missing, so this process remains a research gap.

The third stage, 'emerging academic science', begins with the establishment of chairs at universities. If the holders of these first chairs succeed, among other things, in establishing a training programme in the form of a university-based course of study, ensuring stable self-recruitment from their own young scientists and subsequently promoting a quantitative expansion of academic discipline, then the fourth stage of 'established science' has been reached and this is exactly what we are focusing in our current contribution (see figure 1).

Figure 1 Clark's stage model of the institutionalisation process of scientific disciplines and our focus on the established science, Source: Own presentation based on Clark (1972)

As already quoted at the beginning, Reinisch (2009) explicates in his scientific sociological analysis of the vocational and business education that it has achieved the status of an established science decades ago. But an empirical examination of Reinisch's determination of

³ In view of the continuation and completion of the data collection and against the background of an empirical foundation of generation classification or another grouping or periodisation that is still outstanding, our findings are to be regarded as preliminary.

⁴ The restriction to business education is to be legitimized on the one hand by an interim research pragmatic limitation and our work progress and on the other hand by the non-simultaneity of the academic constitution and the development of business and vocational education (cf. chapter 1).

the degree of institutionalisation of the vocational and business education or establishment thesis of the VET is pending.

In his remarks, he not only assigns the VET the status of an established science, but also marks a period of time in which the transition has taken place. With the term ‘decades’, which he has chosen but not specified in more detail, he focuses in our understanding on a period 30-40 years ago, ca. 1970 to 1980. The basis on which he makes this assessment remains open and implicitly raises the question of whether the VET is actually an established science or scientific (partial) discipline because Reinisch can only prove this to a limited extent. In addition, the question arises from which period of time onwards we can consider the focused VET as an established science or an established educational science (partial) discipline.

Nevertheless, Reinisch was not the only one in the VET who dealt with the development of his own field. Another well-known representative was Zabeck (2006), who dealt with the question of generation classification within the VET and distinguished between three generations. A first generation, whose initial appointment took place before 1955/60; a second generation from about 1955/60 and a third generation since 1985/90 (Zabeck, 2009a; 2009b).

Against the background of Zabeck’s generational classification, we have based our analyses on a (preliminary) generational span of 30 years⁵, starting from the first chair for ‘Handelsschulpädagogik und betriebswirtschaftliche Nachbargebiete’ (transl. ‘commercial school education and commercial science neighbouring areas’) at the ‘Handelshochschule Leipzig’ (transl. ‘Higher education institution of commerce Leipzig’) and the first professor Karl von der Aa (1876 - 1937) in 1923, according to prevailing doctrine (e.g. Reinisch 2009). This makes it possible to carry out the following analyses within the first three generations:

- Generation 1: Initial appointment 1923-1953
- Generation 2: Initial appointment 1954-1984
- Generation 3: Initial appointment 1985-2015
- (*Generation 4: Initial appointment after 2016*)

In this respect, the research question, we are looking at here, can be concretized as follows:

- (F1) From which generation onwards can VET (resp. business and/or vocational education) be described as an established science or partial discipline(s) of educational science (in the sense of Clark, 1972; 1974)?

3. Methods

In order to answer the research question (F1), a collective-biographical data corpus (Schröder, 2011) was created, in which e.g. data on the academic qualifications and employment relationships as well as on professional scientific employment (including appointments and de-

⁵ This classification is to be regarded as an attempt in creating meaningful grouping, periodisation or processualisation, which is not only debatable from the perspective of social science research, but also from the historian’s point of view, as he stands methodically on clay feet like all process-contemplating interpretations of history and must first prove to be able to reach a consensus through further investigations (Schulze, 2002). Nevertheless, it offers the advantage of systematisation. We also regard the generation classification as provisional, since the development of a suitable network-analytical method for the empirical foundation of the generation classification or grouping is still pending.

nominations) are included. The following data collection strategy (see figure 2) was used to establish the data set. It is characterised by a complete analysis of easily accessible fundamental VET sources with extensive biographical information on professors of the discipline. Finally, missing were determined and complemented by a complementary analysis as far as possible.

Figure 2 Data collection strategy, Source: Own presentation

Based on this collective-biographical data set, we created a network by the visualisation and exploration software Gephi (see figure 3). It covers the qualification and employment relationships of the professors of the VET in the German-speaking area.

Figure 3 Enlarged detail of a first test plot of the network of VET professors, Source: Own presentation based on the collective-biographical data set (status: Dec. 2018)

For the visualisation we used the Event Graph Layout (Spekkink, 2016). This enabled us to arrange the network on the x-axis according to the year of initial appointment and on the y-axis according to the ForceAtlas2 algorithm (Jacomy et al., 2014) for spatial representation. The classification of the professors according to disciplines is based on the classification by ‘Kürschners Deutscher Gelehrtenkalender’ (2018). Each network node represents a professor

and each arrow or pointed edge represents a relation or some relationships to an academic teacher. The size of the labels of the nodes represents the indegree. So the larger the label of the node, the more connections due to employment and/or qualification relations of subsequent professors are present at this node. The same applies to the arrows. So the larger the arrow, the more employment and qualification relationships between the professors and their academic teacher are presented. The dividing dotted vertical line marks the transition from the second to the third generation (cf. chapter 2).

4. Preliminary results for business education as a part of VET

Clark's model (cf. chapter 2) focuses on the quantitative development of a discipline, its social network and the ability to self-recruit. Based on the research question (F1) and against the background of the Clark stage model, the following four hypotheses⁶ can be derived for business education (N=93) as a part of VET (see chapter 1 and footnote 4), which are then to be examined over the generations G1, G2 and G3.

On the basis of the hypothesis test (H1-H4) over the three generations (G1, G2 and G3) of the business education, the period during which the business education is established as a science or (partial-) discipline of VET and educational science can be delimited as follows (see table 1).

Table 1 Limitation of the establishment period of the business education (over generations), Source: Collective-biographical data set (status: Sept. 2017)

Hypotheses	G1 (1923- 1953)	G2 (1954- 1984)	G3 (1985- 2015)
(H1) In the progressing establishment process, the number of the business education professors increases.	X	✓	✓
(H2) In the progressing establishment process, the initial appointment age of the business education professors decreases.	X	✓	(✓) rel. stable
(H3) In the progressing establishment process, the number of qualification and/or employment relationships between the business education professors increases.	X	✓	(✓) expectable
(H4) In the progressing establishment process, the relative share of non-discipline professors who are in qualification and/or employment relationships with professors of the business education decreases.	X	X	✓

Starting from table 1, the establishment of the business education can be located at the transition from G2 to G3 - i.e. around 1985. In G3, the business education can therefore be described as an established science or educational science (partial-) discipline within the frame of the Clark model. This largely corresponds to Reinisch's assessment (cf. chapter 2). However, it should be noted critically that this first limitation of the establishment period of the business education or the partial answering of F1 should be regarded as provisional in

⁶ For a detailed description of the hypothesis test, see Götzl, Geiser, & Jahn, 2018.

view of the underlying generational classification, missing and/or incomplete data (in particular for vocational education) and more comprehensive studies (e.g. in conjunction with publication analyses). In this respect, we are only at the beginning of our research work and may have to revise or specify this finding in the future.

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